

Synthesis, Characterisation and Reactions of Dichlorotrakis(4-t-butylphenoxo)tantalum(v) with α -Hydroxyaldehydes and Ketones

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Dichlorotrakis(4-t-butylphenoxo)tantalum(v) (1) has been synthesised by reacting tantalum pentachloride and 4-t-butylphenol in 1 : 3 molar ratio in dry benzene under reflux and characterised by elemental analysis, conductance, ir, nmr and mass spectral studies. Reaction of 1 with equimolar amounts of hydroxyl containing substrates having labile protons, such as benzoin, 2-hydroxyacetophenone and salicylaldehyde in 1 : 1 molar ratio, yielded six-coordinate complexes of composition $TaCl_2(OC_6H_4Bu^t-4)_3 \cdot L$.

Many examples of metal complexes containing alkoxide and phenoxide ligands are available in literature^{1,2}. Compared to alkoxide ligands, aryloxy ligands are known to have a general advantage in that their electronic and steric properties can be easily varied by changing the substituents on the ring and have been widely used in the field of organometallic chemistry related to metathesis. In particular, the pentaphenoxides of niobium and tantalum were first isolated by Funk and Baumann³. Among a variety of phenoxide complexes for tantalum(v), $Ta(OPh)_5$ and mixed chlorophenoxides $[TaCl_{5-x}(OPh)_x]$ have been reported to be synthesised from $TaCl_5$ and phenol^{2,4}. Much of the recent interest in the synthesis of metal complexes containing bulky substituents at different positions of phenoxide phenyl ring has been stimulated by various reports in which mention has been made of the resulting unusual geometries and coordinatively unsaturated molecules^{5,6}. Recently, a number of sterically congested trisphenoxide complexes of tantalum(v) have been reported to be formed between a series of lithium 2,6-disubstituted phenoxides and $TaCl_5$ ⁷. Recently we have described⁸ the synthesis and reactivity of $Ta(OC_6H_4Bu^t-4)_5$. In the present communication, we describe the synthesis of $TaCl_2(OC_6H_4Bu^t-4)_3$ using tantalum pentachloride and 4-t-butylphenol (4-Bu^tC₆H₄OH) (1). The reactivity of 1 with α -hydroxyaldehydes and ketones with hydroxyl containing substrates having labile proton, which are known to form fairly stable chelates with alkoxides and phenoxides⁹ has also been investigated.

Results and Discussion

Formation of compound 1 by the reaction of $TaCl_5$ with 4-t-butylphenol can be rationalised as shown in the scheme. The compound was found soluble in most of the organic solvents. Stoichiometric composition of the compound has been established by elemental analysis (Table 1). Molar con-

ductance of millimolar solution of this compound in nitrobenzene is too low ($1.26 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) to be attributed to an electrolyte, while molecular weight determination in the same solvent indicates that it exists as a monomer in contrast to tantalum(v) phenoxides and naphthoxides reported to be dimeric^{4,10}.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd* (Colour/m.p. °C)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Mol. wt. ** Found/ Calcd.)
	Ta	Cl	C	H	
$TaCl_2(OC_6H_4Bu^t-4)_3$ (Yellow, 263)	25.84 (25.93)	10.12 10.17	51.50 51.57	5.52 5.58	680 698)
$TaCl_2(OC_6H_4Bu^t-4)_3 \cdot Sal^a$ (Yellow, 72)	23.01 (23.08)	4.44 4.52	56.57 56.63	5.54 5.61	768 784)
$TaCl_2(OC_6H_4Bu^t-4)_3 \cdot Benz^a$ (Brown, 68)	20.70 (20.73)	4.04 4.06	60.40 60.48	5.52 5.61	856 873)
$TaCl_2(OC_6H_4Bu^t-4)_3 \cdot Hap^a$ (Yellow, 58)	22.60 (22.68)	4.40 4.44	57.10 57.14	5.72 5.76	778 798)

(*SalH=Salicylaldehyde; BenzH=Benzoin; HapH=2-Hydroxyacetophenone. **Mean of three determinations.

The ¹H nmr spectrum of compound 1 does not show any phenolic resonance, indicating thereby

deprotonation of phenolic proton on reacting with $TaCl_5$. A single resonance for the methyl protons of *t*-butyl group is observed at δ 1.25. A slight upfield shift of the ring protons *ortho* and *meta* to phenoxy oxygen is evidenced from the appearance of these resonances at δ 7.18 and 6.65 in $TaCl_5(OC_6H_4Bu^t-4)_3$, compared with the free ligand resonances at δ 7.23 and 6.75 respectively. These observations may be tentatively assigned to the overall π -bonding properties of the phenoxide ligand as has been reported by Clark and coworkers¹¹ for $TaCl_5(2,6\text{-di-}t\text{-butylphenoxide})_2$ and $TaCl_5(2,6\text{-di-}t\text{-butylphenoxide})_3$ respectively.

The ir band due to OH in the free ligand is absent and the ν_{CO} band ($1\ 225\text{ cm}^{-1}$) in pure 4-*t*-butylphenol is significantly lowered by 64 cm^{-1} on compound formation. This suggests that loss of phenolic proton as HCl gas is followed by coordination of the ligand through oxygen. This is further substantiated by the appearance of new bands at $530\text{--}550\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assigned to $\nu_{(Ta-O)}$ modes. Any possibility of polymerisation of aryloxides through aryloxo group was excluded due to the absence of $Ta/O \rightarrow Ta$ band expected in the range $470\text{--}490\text{ cm}^{-1}$, much lower than terminal ν_{Ta-O} mode.

In the mass spectrum of compound **1**, the molecular ion peak $[M]^+$ is observed at m/z 698 which is in conformity with the information given by molecular weight and ir spectral studies. Thus based upon the limited data available, compound **1** may be considered to assume a trigonal bipyramidal geometry shown below :

and is supported by the earlier reports on similar compounds⁶.

Reactions of 1 with α -hydroxyaldehydes and ketones : Reactions of **1** with α -hydroxyaldehydes and ketones in 1 : 1 molar ratio leading to the formation of chelate compounds may be considered to occur through the following route,

where L is the anion of chelating ligands.

Elemental analyses of the complexes are in accordance with the desired stoichiometry (Table 1). All the complexes are sharp melting solids and fairly soluble in common organic solvents like the

parent compound. Molar conductance values of their millimolar solutions (in nitrobenzene) suggest them to be non-electrolytes. Molecular weights of the complexes determined by cryoscopic method (in nitrobenzene) show their monomeric nature.

In the ir spectra of complexes, the absence of bands due to ν_{OH} mode present at $3\ 390$, $3\ 410$ and $3\ 180\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in benzoin, 2-hydroxyacetophenone and salicylaldehyde and a significant lowering of ν_{CO} band from $1\ 090\text{--}1\ 110\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the free ligands to $1\ 065\text{--}1\ 080\text{ cm}^{-1}$ on complexation, indicate deprotonation of phenolic OH, accompanied by coordination through phenolic oxygen of the hydroxyl group. In addition, coordination from carbonyl oxygen to tantalum is also indicated by a significant lowering of carbonyl stretching modes observed at $1\ 640\text{--}1\ 680\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the free ligands to $1\ 590\text{--}1\ 630\text{ cm}^{-1}$. This is in agreement with the earlier reports on the similar chelate complexes¹². Based upon these limited data, an octahedral structure may be proposed for the chelates as

Experimental

Tantalum(v) pentachloride (correct chlorine analysis) was used as such without further purification. 4-*t*-Butylphenol was used after crystallisation from benzene. Benzoin, 2-hydroxyacetophenone and salicylaldehyde were purified by standard methods. Benzene and nitrobenzene were distilled before use. Tantalum was estimated as Ta_2O_5 while chlorine by Volhard's method. Ir spectra (KBr/nujol) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 337 and 621 spectrophotometers. ¹H nmr spectra on a Varian EM-360 spectrometer using TMS as internal indicator and mass spectra on a Varian MAT-711 spectrometer. Molecular weight was determined cryoscopically in nitrobenzene. Conductance was measured on an Elico conductivity bridge.

Dichlorotris(4-*t*-butylphenoxy)tantalum(v), $TaCl_2(OC_6H_4Bu^t-4)_3$ (1): A mixture of tantalum pentachloride (2.0 g, 2 mol) dissolved in dry benzene (200 ml) and 4-*t*-butylphenol (2.514 g, 6 mol) was refluxed for 58 h until the evolution of HCl gas ceased. The resulting clear solution was concentrated by removing the solvent and allowed to stand overnight when a yellow solid separated out which was crystallised from ether and dried under

reduced pressure (3.690 g), m.p. 263°. All manipulations were done in an inert atmosphere.

Reactions of dichlorotris(4-t-butylphenol) tantalum(v) with α -hydroxyaldehydes and ketones: The chelates of composition $TaCl(OC_6H_4Bu^t-4)_3 \cdot L$ (L=anion of benzoin, salicylaldehyde and 2-hydroxyacetophenone) were prepared by reacting 1 with an equimolar amounts of chelating reagents in dry benzene. On addition of the chelating reagent a colour change of the solution was observed. The contents were stirred for about 24 h. The solid complexes were isolated (yields 78–95%) from the resulting solutions which were first concentrated and left undisturbed overnight.

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